

Development and Characterization of Deflazacort Nanoparticles for the Treatment of Inflammatory Bowel Disease

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ABSTRACT

Inflammatory Bowel Disease (IBD) are difficult to control and the reappearance is the most challenging issue for the physicians. IBD includes Ulcerative colitis (UC) and Crohn's disease (CD). There are various controlled and colon targeted drug delivery systems available for the treatment with a limited success rate. Nanoparticles prepared by using the colon targeted polymers such as chitosan may improve the condition of IBD due to their smaller size, unique physicochemical properties, and targeting potential. Deflazacort is a glucocorticoid used as an anti-inflammatory, immunosuppressant and commonly prescribed drug for the patient having IBD such as Ulcerative Colitis (UC) and Crohn's Disease (CD). The purpose of the present study was to prepare and evaluate the potential of eudragit coated chitosan nanoparticles of Deflazacort for the treatment of IBD by ionic gelation method. These nanoparticles were further coated with Eudragit S-100 by the solvent evaporation technique so as to prevent drug release in the stomach and small intestine. Developed Nanoparticles were subjected to various characterization techniques such as FTIR, particle size, scanning electron microscopy (SEM), drug entrapment efficiency and zeta potential. The efficiency of drug release from prepared formulation was studied in vitro in gastrointestinal fluids of different pH. The prepared nanoparticles demonstrated the size in the nano range. The release pattern of Deflazacort from eudragit-coated chitosan nanoparticles was observed to be pH dependent. In acidic medium, the release rate was much slower however the drug was released quickly at pH 6.8 and 7.5. Subsequently, stability study at various storage temperature was also done in which the prepared formulation showed improved stability. The zeta potential of the best chitosan preparation (F2) was found to be -30.5 mV, which confirms the stability of prepared nanosuspension. Eudragit-coated chitosan nanoparticles can be a promising carrier for colon-targeted delivery of Deflazacort found to have high encapsulation efficiency and predetermined in vitro drug release profile.

KEY WORDS: Inflammatory Bowel Disease, Deflazacort, ionic gelation method, eudragit-coated

INTRODUCTION:

Deflazacort (1-(1,16)-21-(acetyloxy)-11-hydroxyl-2-methyl-5H-pregna-1,4-dieno[17,16-d]oxazole-3, 20-dione) is a synthetic glucocorticoid and an oxazoline derivative of Prednisolone. It has influential anti-inflammatory activity and immunosuppressive action^[1-2], which is quite analogous to Prednisolone. Deflazacort is a prodrug and is utilized in Duchenne muscular dystrophy (DMD), Rheumatic polymyalgia, Drug-resistant epilepsy of childhood, Idiopathic Nephrotic Syndrome (INS), renal transplant and Asthma^[3]. In India it is sold

under the trade name as Moaid, Zenflav, Defolet, DFZ, Decotaz, and DefZot. The oral route of drug administration is the most convenient and hence the preferred means of drug delivery to the systemic circulation of the body. However, oral administration of most drugs in conventional dosage forms has limitations due to their inability to restrain and localize the drug delivery system at GIT.

Because of smaller size and efficient carrier capacity, Nanotechnology is now becoming an important area of research due to its wide range of benefits in the pharmaceutical industry and applied sciences^[4,5]. Recent research reports revealed the opportunities of nanomedicine in the treatment of IBD. Nanomedicine may replace the conventional dosage forms in the treatment of IBD^[6]. Present treatment of IBD lacks cure (only remission). Nanoparticles are helpful in improving the function of current existing drugs by targeting action, solubility improvement and

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dose reduction^[7]. Various study reports revealed the advantage of nanoformulations for IBD at minimum doses^[8]. Chitosan nanoparticles have gained significant importance since chitosan is the natural colon targeted polymer. Because of its biocompatible properties, chitosan was gravely investigated as a potential drug carrier and is a natural linear biopolyaminosaccharide obtained by alkaline deacetylation of chitin, the second abundant polysaccharide next to cellulose^[9]. Some studies have suggested utilizing chitosan to coat nanoparticles made of other materials to lower down their impact on the body and increase their bioavailability.

The elemental composition of the chitosan polymer is carbon (44.11%), hydrogen (6.84%) and nitrogen (7.97), because of their biocompatibility, biodegradability, low immunogenicity and low cost, chitosan has emerged as an important biomaterial and pharmaceutical excipient for drug delivery^[10].

The formation of chitosan nanoparticles includes a simple and non toxic method known as ionic gelation method. In this method, chitosan polysaccharide is dissolved in aqueous acidic solution to get the cation of chitosan^[11]. The solution formed is then added to the aqueous Sodium tripolyphosphate [STPP] solution under stirring conditions. In this research work, Deflazacort nanoparticles were prepared by high result oriented ionic gelation method with some slight modifications. Chitosan was utilized along with STPP. The formulations are developed with a scope of better therapeutic efficacy, solubility and penetration at the inflamed site.

MATERIALS & METHODS:

Chitosan, Eudragit S-100 was obtained from HiMedia Laboratories Ltd, Mumbai, India. STPP, acetic acid, ethanol, Span 80, acetone, dichloromethane and light liquid paraffin were purchased from Central Drug House Pvt Ltd, Mumbai, India. All other reagents and chemicals used were of analytical grade.

Preformulation Studies:

Solubility:

The Solubility of the drug was determined by weighing approximately 10 mg of drug and transferred to 7 different volumetric flask of 10 ml. Different solvents (Distilled water, 0.1 N HCl, 0.1 N NaOH, Ethanol, Methanol, pH 7.2 phosphate buffer and Chloroform) were made up to mark into the 10 ml flask respectively and shaken vigorously. The solubility was observed at room temperature.

FTIR spectroscopy:

IR spectra of physical mixture of drug and excipients were recorded by KBr method using Fourier Transform Infrared Spectrophotometer. A base line correction was made using dried potassium bromide pellet. The potassium bromide-drug pellet of approximately 1 mm diameter, was prepared by grinding 3-5 mg of physical mixture of drug-excipients with 100-150 mg of potassium bromide in pressure compression machine. The sample pellet was mounted in IR compartment and scanned at wavelengths 4000 cm⁻¹ to 400 cm⁻¹.

Determination of λ_{max} of Deflazacort:

Accurately weighed 10 mg of drug was dissolved in 100 ml of phosphate buffer pH 7.2 in a 100 ml volumetric flask. 0.1 ml of this stock solution was pipetted into a 10 ml volumetric flask and volume was made up to the mark with phosphate buffer pH 7.2. The resulting solution was scanned between 200-400 nm using UV/Vis double beam spectrophotometer. The same procedure was followed for determining the wavelength maxima phosphate buffer pH 7.2.

Fabrication of Deflazacort loaded nanoparticles by ionic gelation technique:

Chitosan nanoparticles were prepared by Ionic gelation method. Chitosan stock solution (1% w/v) was prepared by dissolving chitosan in acetic acid (1% v/v) in a beaker at room temperature. The 5mg of drug Deflazacort was dissolved in chitosan solution in a beaker for around five minutes with the help of a bath sonicator (Indian Machine tools, India). STPP solution (1%) was prepared separately in distilled water. Chitosan nanoparticles were fabricated with the dropwise addition of STPP solution with the help of a syringe to chitosan solution under magnetic stirring at room temperature. The solution was magnetically stirred for half an hour followed by filtration and rinsing with distilled water. The acquired Nanoparticles were air dried for twenty four hours followed by oven drying for six hours at 40°C^[12]. The composition of chitosan nanoparticles is given (Table 1).

Coating of prepared nanoparticles:

With the aid of solvent evaporation method, chitosan nanoparticles were coated with Eudragit S-100 (ES). In 10ml of the coating solution prepared by dissolving 500 mg of ES-100 in ethanol, 50 mg of nanoparticles were dispersed: acetone (2:1) to give 5:1 (coat: core ratio). Subsequently, this organic process was poured in light liquid paraffin containing 1% w/v

Table 1: Formulations of chitosan nanoparticles.

Formulation Code	Deflazacort (mg)	Chitosan (mg)	STPP (mg)
F1	5	250	500
F2	5	250	750
F3	5	250	1000
F4	5	500	500
F5	5	500	750
F6	5	500	1000

Span 80. The system was maintained for 3 hours at room temperature under agitation speed of 1000 rpm which allows the solvent to evaporate. The coated nanoparticles coating were filtered, washed with n-hexane and dried in desiccators^[13].

Evaluation of nanoparticles:

Drug Entrapment Efficiency-

Deflazacort was estimated in Chitosan nanoparticles by ultra centrifugation method. The 10mg of formulation was transferred to 10 ml centrifuge tube and diluted with distilled 10 ml of phosphate buffer (pH 7.2) and centrifuged at 2000 rpm for 20 minutes to separate out undissolved drug in the formulation. Supernatant and nanoparticles (sediment) was recovered and their volume was measured. Nanoparticles was diluted with distilled water upto 5ml. The untrapped and entrapped drug contents were analyzed by estimating drug in supernatant and nanoparticles by spectroscopic method. The percentage of drug entrapment and yield was calculated as:

$$\% \text{ drug entrapment} = \text{calculated drug content} / \text{theoretical drug content} \times 100$$

Measurement of mean particle size-

The mean particle size of the nanoparticles was determined by Photo Correlation Spectroscopy (PCS) on a submicron particle size analyzer (Malvern particle size analyzer) at a scattering angle of 90°. A sample (0.5mg) of the nanoparticles was dragged in 5 ml of distilled water which was used for the measurement.

Determination of zeta potential-

The zeta potential of the drug-loaded nanoparticles was measured on a zeta sizer (Malvern particle size analyser) by determining the electrophoretic mobility in a micro electrophoresis flow cell. All the samples were measured in water at 25°C in triplicate.

Shape and surface morphology-

From the formulated batches of nanoparticles, formulations (F2) which exhibited an appropriate balance between the percentage of drug releases was examined for shape and surface morphology with the help of a scanning electron microscope (Jeol Japan 6000). The Sample was fixed on carbon tape and fine gold sputtering was applied in a high vacuum evaporator. The acceleration voltage was set at 10KV during scanning. Microphotographs were taken on different magnification and higher magnification (200X) was used for surface morphology.

In-Vitro Drug Release-

The prepared nanoparticles were evaluated for in vitro drug release by using USP I Basket type dissolution test apparatus. An accurately weighed quantity of formulation (equivalent to 30mg) was filled in capsule and kept in the basket of dissolution apparatus with the dissolution media (900 ml) at 37±0.2°C. Samples were withdrawn at a different time interval and compensated with same amount of fresh dissolution media. The Volume of sample withdrawn was made up to 5ml by dissolution media. The samples withdrawn were assayed spectrophotometrically at 242 nm for percentage release of Deflazacort using UV visible spectrophotometer. The release of Deflazacort was calculated with the help of a standard curve of Deflazacort. The scheme of using the simulated fluids at different timing was as follows:

1st hour: Simulated gastric fluid (SGF) of pH 1.2.

2nd and 3rd hour: Mixture of simulated gastric and

Intestinal fluid of pH 4.5.

4th to 5th hour: Simulated intestinal fluid (SIF) of pH 6.8

6th hour and onward: SIF pH 7.5

Drug release kinetic data analysis-

Several kinetic models have been proposed to describe the release characteristics of a drug from the matrix. The following four equations are commonly used, because of their simplicity and applicability. Equation 1, the zero-order model equation (Plotted as cumulative percentage of drug released vs time); Equation 2, the first-order model equation (Plotted as log cumulative percent Drug remaining Vs time); Equation 3, Higuchi's square-root equation (Plotted as cumulative percentage of drug released vs square root of time); and Equation 4, the Korsmeyer-Peppas equation (Plotted as Log cumulative percentage of drug released vs Log time).

Stability studies for optimized formulation-

Stability of a formulation on storage is of great concern as it is the major restraint in their development as marketed preparation. Optimized nanoparticle formulation (F2) were stored in amber colored bottles thus subjected to exhaustive stability testing at $4\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ and room temperature for 3 month period. Samples were withdrawn periodically and formulation was observed on the basis of % EE, average particle size and physical appearance.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION:

Deflazacort was freely soluble in ethanol, methanol, 0.1 N NaOH & phosphate buffer pH 7.2. and practically insoluble in 0.1 N HCl, distilled water. Identification of Deflazacort was concluded by FTIR spectroscopy with respect to marker compound. It was identified from the result of IR spectrum as per specification in (Figure 1). The calibration curve of Deflazacort was found to be linear in the concentration range of 10-30 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ at 242 nm (Figure 2).

Figure 1: FT-IR Spectrum of Pure Drug (Deflazacort).

Figure 2: Wavelength maxima of Deflazacort in phosphate buffer pH 7.2

Percentage yield of the different formulation was determined by weighing the nanoparticles after drying. The percentage yield of the different formulation was in the range of 68.89-75.65%. The drug entrapment of different formulations was in the range of 63.23-73.23% w/w. This is due to the mucoadhesion characteristics of chitosan that could

facilitate the diffusion of part of entrapped drug to the surrounding medium during the preparation of Deflazacort nanoparticles. The maximum percentage yield and entrapment efficiency were found in formulation F2 (Table 2).

Table 2: Percentage yield and Entrapment efficiency for different formulation.

Formulation	% Percentage Yield	% EE of Nanoparticles
F ₁	72.25 \pm 0.45	65.56 \pm 0.32
F ₂	75.65 \pm 0.32	73.23 \pm 0.45
F ₃	69.98 \pm 0.52	70.12 \pm 0.45
F ₄	69.45 \pm 0.65	68.85 \pm 0.65
F ₅	68.89 \pm 0.12	65.45 \pm 0.56
F ₆	70.12 \pm 0.54	63.23 \pm 0.41

The mean size of the nanoparticles was determined by photo correlation spectroscopy (PCS) on a submicron particle size analyzer (Particle Size Analyzer from Malvern) at a scattering angle of 90°C . The results of measurement of mean particle size of optimized formulation F2 nanoparticles were found 110.23 nm and zeta potential of optimized formulation F2 nanoparticles was found to be -30.5 mV (Figure 3).

(A)

(B)

Figure 3: Particle size (A) Zeta potential (B) of chitosan nanoparticle (F2).

Table 3: Cumulative % drug release of Deflazacort from plain and eudragit S100 coated nanoparticles at different pH.

S. No.	Dissolution medium	Time (hrs)	% Cumulative Drug Release	
			Chitosan Nanoparticle	Eudragit S100 Coated Nanoparticle
1	SGF (pH 1.2)	1	11.25	4.12
2		2	22.25	5.65
3		3	30.12	8.15
4	SGF+SIF(pH 4.5)	4	36.65	9.95
5		5	45.65	12.12
6		6	60.12	22.12
7	SIF (pH 6.8)	7	65.23	38.89
8		8	69.98	45.65
9	SIF (pH 7.5)	9	72.12	60.23
10		10	75.65	70.23
11		12	80.23	82.98

The SEM photomicrographs of the chitosan nanoparticles were taken and characterized in terms of sphericity and particles clumping. As observed in photomicrograph the nanoparticles having a smooth surface and perfectly spherical (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Scanning Electronic Microscopy of optimized formulation (F2).

An *In-vitro* dissolution study was conducted to study the *in-vitro* drug release profile of plain and coated nanoparticle. As the purpose of this formulation was to avoid the release of drug in the gastric and upper intestinal region but to release the drug slowly in the lower part of the intestine maximizing drug concentration in the colon, the *in-vitro* drug release study was conducted at different pH using USP protocol. The obtained results are shown in (Tables 3) while presented in Figure 5 respectively.

The fabricated chitosan nanoparticles were subjected to the study of drug release kinetics and

Figure 5: Graph of cumulative % drug release of deflazacort from chitosan and eudragit S100 coated nanoparticles.

release mechanism. The *in-vitro* release data for optimized formulations F2 was analyzed for zero order, Higuchi and Korsmeyer-Peppas models. Based on the correlation co-efficient (r^2) best fitted model was selected (Table 4).

The average particle size of nanoparticle was found 110.23 ± 0.23 , 118.56 ± 0.36 and 135.65 ± 0.32 nm after 1, 2 and 3 month of storage at $4.0 \pm 0.2^\circ\text{C}$ while at $25-28 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ the average vesicle size was found 125.32 ± 0.45 , 145.65 ± 0.45 and 186.65 ± 0.54 nm after 1, 2 and 3 month of storage. % EE in nanoparticle formulation was 65.56 ± 0.32 , 60.54 ± 0.36 and $55.65 \pm 0.56\%$ after 1, 2 and 3 month of storage at $25-28 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ while there were no significant changes in % EE and physical appearance in nanoparticle formulation was observed after 3 month of storage at 4°C (Table 5).

Table 4: Regression Analysis Data of nanoparticle Formulation.

Formulation	Zero order	First order	Pappas plot
F2	$y = 7.644x - 14.33$ $R^2 = 0.905$	$y = -0.053x + 2.126$ $R^2 = 0.841$	$y = 1.316x + 0.394$ $R^2 = 0.885$

Table 5: Characterization of stability study of Optimized formulation of nanoparticle F2.

Characteristic	Time (Month)					
	1 Month		2 Month		3 Month	
Temperature	4.0 ±0. 2°C	25-28±2°C	4.0 ±0. 2°C	25-28±0. 2°C	4.0 ±0. 2°C	25-28±2°C
Average particle size (nm)	110.23 ±0.23	125.32 ±0.45	118.56 ±0.36	145.65 ±0.45	135.65 ±0.32	186.65 ±0.54
% EE	73.23 ±0.23	65.56 ±0.32	71.45 ±0.54	60.54 ±0.36	69.98 ±0.45	55.65 ±0.56
Physical Appearance	Normal	Normal	Normal	Normal	Normal	Normal

CONCLUSION:

The data generated as an outcome of this article demonstrates that the stable colon targeted Eudragit S-100 coated deflazacort nanoparticles with chitosan for the treatment of IBD was developed. The successful preparation of nanoparticles was established by characterization analysis. The maximum percentage yield and drug content was found 75.65±0.32 and 73.23±0.45 respectively in formulation F2. The lowest particle size entrapped the higher drug content as compared to the other formulations. Also *in vitro* studies of uncoated and eudragit S100 coated nanoparticles was carried out in simulated gastrointestinal fluid medium of different pH. Cumulative percentage drug released was found from various optimized formulation at different time intervals. In case of chitosan coated nanoparticles nearly 36.65–45.65% of the drug released in initial 4–5 h. This situation is best suited in condition where drug is required to be absorbed or remain in the upper part of GIT. As far as treatment of colonic disease is concerned, it is important to ensure the delivery of drug in intact form in the vicinity of target organ.

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